

ESL Practitioners' Autonomy: A Comparative Study of School, College and University Instructors in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT: Teacher's autonomy is an aspect of the pedagogical process which highly affects a teacher's performance not only at school and college but also at university level. Teachers being in direct contact with their pupils know them better than administration. Hence, they are in better position to take decisions about the student related matters as course contents, medium of assessment etc.

Teachers deal with many challenges as learners of different abilities and administration of their institution. With a focus on ESL instructors, this study intends to reveal the practices related to teachers' autonomy support, their workplace environment and their classroom practices related to language learners to shed light on the challenges faced by them in this process. In this research, three experienced teachers working at the school, college and university were interviewed. Semi-structured interviews were conducted to find out the extent to which the teachers have autonomy in terms of pedagogical matters and in terms of their relationship with administrative bodies. They were also asked the extent to which they help their learners become autonomous. Thus the aim of the present study is to find out that at what level; primary, secondary or tertiary ESL practitioners have more autonomy. This factor is in need to be investigated to provide a better insight into the prevailing situation of academic discourse community in Pakistan. Hence, understanding the present situation may provide a direction for proposing applicable suggestions because the teachers' autonomy is one of the important factors affecting the learning of language learners.

Keywords: Teachers' autonomy, comparison, administration,

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1. Introduction

1.1. Education:

Education is of central value for the development of not only individuals but also of nations. It is the phenomenon which has gained the undeniable value across the globe. Education is the preliminary point as well as the final goal of a nation. In the present world, English has become the language of communication around the world. It has achieved status of language of education, business, politics and international relations. Hence, English language proficiency has been associated with success in all spheres of life: in academic as well as in occupational discourse communities. It is because of this reason that teaching English as second and foreign English has been the point of focus of academic and research communities in almost all the countries of the world. Consequently, Education sector is facing challenges in meeting the worldwide demands and expectations of the present age.

1.2. Context of the Study:

As far as the context of the present study is concerned, Pakistan is a land rich with many languages (Rahman, 2002). There are numerous local languages and Urdu is the national language. The colonial history of the country and status of English as international language has made it important and prestigious language and it makes the language issue more complex. It is also the official language of the country. This complexity of linguistic diversity in Pakistani culture has permeated in the education system as well leading to significance of English language teaching and learning. Evidently the importance of English cannot be undervalued in Pakistani milieu. English language being the official language of Pakistan, taught formally in the educational institutions of Pakistan as a core subject at primary and secondary level. Additionally, it is the medium of instruction at tertiary level. It is the language of all the socio-economic spheres and holds great importance academically as well (Rahman, 2002). Thus English language competence is a gateway to economic and social success in the country (Quraishi et al.p.83).

1.3. Teachers:

Teacher is considered as a central figure in academic settings. His skill greatly influences the students' academic performance and personality development. Therefore, teachers' competence and skills stand as the decisive force on the continuum of the improvement of academic institution (Jumani and Malik, 2017).

Moreover, teachers not only serve to impart knowledge, but also work as “managers, planners, facilitators” and role-model for their students (Wermke, p. 308). Teachers are responsible for teaching social values and ethics to the students. Therefore, their value cannot be underestimated for personality development of students (Ingersoll and Collins, 2017, p.75). Hence, teachers have many professional responsibilities. However, these duties slightly vary subject to the level they are teaching. At school and college level, they are not required to divert their energies for research. It is because of the fact that they are promoted on the basis of experience, not research. On the contrary, at university level teachers are required to pursue higher studies and publish their research regularly. It is a

pre requisite for their promotion. Thus they are not only supposed to impart knowledge but also to create and add to the existing body of knowledge. "Publish or perish" is the criteria in the universities.

As tutors at all levels, are in direct and continuous contact with their students, therefore they better understand learners' needs (Johari, et al, 2018, p.7). So, in order to perform their duties successfully, instructors need to be given more autonomy in their professional domain as they are required to make decisions about the education of their students, particularly in terms of determining the syllabus and teaching strategies (Johari et al.2018, p.3). They are placed between the learners and the administration and their different expectations (Ingersoll, 2011, p. 103).

Although, their role is highly influential but it is dependent on the education politics of the country or of the institution (Erss, 2017, p.5). During the last twenty years, the relationship of tutors' autonomy with control exercised by administrative bodies has often been typified as "competing discourses" (Erss and Kalmus, 2018, p. 96). Recently, the literature pertaining to teachers' own perceptions of autonomy has become the focus of attention (Paradis, et al. 2019, p.2).

1.4. Autonomy:

Teacher autonomy is one of the most popular but complex ideas to have emerged in contemporary research at wider global level. Erss (2017) states that Allwright presented this notion (1990) which was later established by Little (1995). According to Ryan & Deci, (2006), autonomy is one of the motivational factors for teachers. Autonomy is seen as "governance by self as opposed to heteronomy" which denotes regulations from outside (Erss, 2017, p.2). To put it another way, autonomy is "capacity and responsibilities to bring, change and manage one's attitudes and capabilities in a productive way. Teachers possess autonomy when they are able to have control over any situation and possess freedom to handle all matters using their own approach" (Jumani and Malik, 2017, p. 31). The notion is perceived differently in language teaching where it predominantly denotes teachers' freedom regarding curriculum syllabus and classroom activities. Autonomy in pedagogy incepted in the mid1970s. However, interest in autonomy has grown considerably since the beginning of the 21st century (Benson, 2007, p.21). The recent literature on the topic relates teachers' autonomy with learner's autonomy (Benson, 2007, p. 30). In other words, teacher autonomy has been related to positive effects on their efficiency (Salokangas, et al. 2020, p. 2).

Teacher autonomy is "a multidimensional context-dependent phenomenon" (Salokangas, et al. 2020, p.4). There are various domains and levels of teachers' perceived autonomy. They are pedagogical and organizational aspect of autonomy. They vary depending on context and setting of the academic institution.

The life in educational institutions particularly of tutors is very complex. In other words, the context is diverse in different academic settings which complicates the comparison of these phenomena. Here in order to reduce its complexity and make it empirically investigable, the current research emphasizes on autonomy as aspects of

decision-making in terms of classroom and pedagogical matters and decision making regarding administrative work (Wermke, 2019. p.308).

1.5. Statement of the Problem:

The comparative aspect of ESL tutors' autonomy is the understudied area. Therefore this is the centroid of research study under question. This factor is in need to be investigated to provide a better insight into the prevailing situation of academic discourse community in Pakistan. A better understanding of any phenomenon is a pre requisite for its transformation and betterment which is the final and ultimate goal of every research. "Teacher autonomy is an important, almost magical, ingredient for a successful school and professional development" (Wermke, et al, 2019, p. 306).

2. Research Objectives

The present study endeavors to provide invaluable insights about teacher perceptions of and attitudes toward autonomy and about the challenges faced by English language teachers. The aim of the present study is to probe into the matter of teacher's autonomy. To specify it further, the purpose of the study is to find out at which level; out of school, college and university EFL instructors avail more independence.

2.1. Research Questions:

The research questions are as follow:

- i. How are pedagogical decisions for EFL teaching made in the study context?
- ii. To what extent are EFL teachers independent in making decisions about curriculum, methodology, materials and assessment?

3. Literature Review

The concept of instructor autonomy has been extensively researched as delegation of power to instructors in many countries of the world. The extent of control an instructor is allowed by the institution has been studied in China to get a better insight of educational practices (Xu, 2015). The teachers' role in decision making process in American schools is surveyed (Ingersoll, 2011). Another study focused on the impact of context on teacher's autonomy (Paradis et al.2019). Johari, et al. studied the relationship between workload, personal and professional life balance, autonomy, and performance in Malaysia (2018). Yet another research sheds light on Irish and Finnish teachers' opinions of their autonomy (Salokangas, et al, 2020). A seminal work discovered teachers' views about their practice on developing autonomy in their learners. The study also paid heed to EFL teachers' awareness about the concepts of autonomy and knowledge about the basic strategies of learner autonomy (Yasmin and Sohail, 2017). A significant work in this field investigated the benefits of autonomy to teachers and their students (Cheon, et al. 2020). Another considerable work highlighted the teacher autonomy literature and its multifarious nature and contextual situatedness of the phenomenon (Jumani and Malik, 2017). One more research work underscored the value of English as foreign language (EFL) teachers on

learner autonomy and its significance in the foreign language (FL) classrooms, in the Pakistani context (Quraishi, et al.). Another study has publicized that the development of tutor autonomy is linked to instructors' educational practices. In another work, teacher's decision-making skills are viewed and the power relations between instructors, pupils and administration (Wermke, 2019).

Thus, it may be noticed that notwithstanding the importance of the teachers' autonomy and its insinuation on learners' better learning, to date fairly little work has focused on institutional practices supporting teacher's autonomy. Though, a considerable body of research focused on the teachers' autonomy, but prior research investigated the matter on micro level, aiming at one level of primary, secondary or tertiary level. In other words, despite a substantial body of research has focused on teachers' autonomy, the comparative aspect is the understudied area on the topic. This factor is in need to be investigated to provide a better insight into the prevailing situation of academic discourse community in Pakistan. As stated earlier, a better understanding of any phenomenon is a mandatory for its transformation and betterment which is the final and ultimate goal of every research.

4. Methodology

4.1. Purpose of the study:

The aim of the present study is to investigate the degree of autonomy given to ESL instructors in Pakistani institutions at three levels; primary, secondary and tertiary. The issue is highly significant because it influences the pupils' learning outcomes.

4.2. Research Paradigm:

Ontology examines the nature of reality. It emphasizes on what reality is. Epistemology is nature of knowing. It addresses the question how I can know the reality. These two, ontology and epistemology together provide a holistic view of research paradigm. There is another important component of research paradigm, that is, axiology. It denotes the ethical concerns involved in the research under planning. Research paradigms exert substantial effects on a research project. The selection of a paradigm for a research work determines a particular epistemology, ontology, and these elements therefore lead the researcher towards a specific methodology. Thus this holistic view of paradigm infuses the research objectives, questions, participants' selection, data collection tools and data analysis techniques (Kivunja, and Kuyini, 2017, p.38).

The study under question situates into the constructivist paradigm. The main emphasis of the constructivist paradigm is to comprehend "the subjective world of human experience". It advocates that social world cannot be understood from the perspective of an individual and that realities are numerous and socially constructed and socially situated. In addition, context is very significant for knowing. The interpretivist paradigm focuses on understanding the individuals and their views about the world. In this paradigm, "theory does not precede research but follows it so that it is grounded on the data generated by the research act" (Kivunja, and Kuyini, 2017, p.33). The present research falls under the

constructivist paradigm because its focus is subjective experience of ESL practitioners. As mentioned above, the realities are multiple and socially constructed, the teachers' experiences vary from person to person, therefore, they are multiple. In addition, their experiences are different depending on the context that is place, institution and society, so they are socially constructed. Furthermore, as in constructivist paradigm, no theory is preceding the investigation in the present research.

4.3. Research Approach:

The constructivist paradigm supports methods which collect and analyze qualitative data. Hence, the current study is qualitative in nature where the role of researcher is of an instrument of data collection. He is not at a distance from his research rather he himself is in direct contact with the participants and he is the one who is collecting the data personally.

4.4. Data Collection:

One-on-one semi-structured interviews are deemed suitable as the data collection instrument in qualitative research work. Interviews are conducted in English language. The audio-recorded interviews are transcribed and then the verbatim transcriptions are analyzed according to thematic analysis. "The recording and verbatim transcription of interviews is often considered to be one of the more tedious but necessary aspects of the in-depth qualitative research process" (Loubere, 2017, p.1).

Three experienced ESL practitioners were interviewed; one from primary, secondary and tertiary level each. They all serve in public sector institutions. The experience of all participants ranges from ten to fifteen years of teaching. Each participant was distinguished with a number (for example, P1=Participant 1) to protect their anonymity.

Table 1: Participant demographic details and interview durations

Participant	Gender	Age	Years of Experience	Level where the participant teaches	The Highest degree	Interview Duration (In minutes)
P1	Female	35	13	University	MS English	20 minutes
P2	Female	40	15	College	MS English, M Ed.	16 minutes
P3	Female	36	11	School	MA English	13 minutes

The interview questions are categorized in the two parts. In the first part, the researcher aimed to elicit information about the teachers' relationship with administrative aspect of their job. In the next part, interviewer queried about the participants' pedagogical practices. Friedman (1999) states them as organizational and pedagogical autonomy. The former part refers to organizational and the latter denotes to pedagogical autonomy (Erss, 2018, p. 4).

4.5. Ethical Considerations:

The participation was voluntary and the participants were guaranteed anonymity before the commencement of the interviews. The confidentiality of the information they have

provided in the interviews was also assured. Then they signed informed consent forms protecting the rights of the participants. The interviews lasted for about 15-20 minutes each.

4.6. Validity and Trustworthiness:

The choice of validity procedures depends on the paradigms of the research. According to constructivism reality is multiple, open-ended, and socially constructed. The research participants also believe in the multiplicity and contextual aspect of reality. There are two lenses used to validate the research. They are research participants and individuals external to the research. The first one recommends the value of examining how exactly participants' realities have been signified in the interpretation. This is called member checking.

Through this lens the accuracy of the interpretations of the participants is judged. In this way the validity of the research is emphasized by participants. Resultantly, this provides a genuine research account to the audience of the research, that is, ESL practitioners and researcher in the field (Creswell and Miller, 2000, p.125).

4.7. Peer Debriefing:

Peer debriefing is a useful strategy for educators to improve their pedagogical techniques and for researchers to enhance credibility in the qualitative research (Hail, 2011, p.75). Moreover, it is also the second lens for validating the research (Creswell and Miller, 2000, p.125). The interpretation of data by a single researcher may not be objective; therefore, a knowledgeable outside observer may give a more impartial opinion about the proceedings of the research in general and the interpretation of data in particular. Hail et al. (2011) cite Lincoln and Guba (1985) who define peer debriefing as a process where the researcher discusses the research design to an unbiased peer (p. 308). An impartial peer is someone who is a reviewer not affiliated with the research. S/he is not a direct "stakeholder" in the result of a research, but who is a well-informed source on the issue (Hail, et al. 2011, p. 74).

For the study under consideration, opinion of two ESL instructors working in a university situated in Islamabad have been taken. They have been consulted in the beginning to discuss the whole research design. Later their considerations have been taken about the analysis of the data.

4.8. Member checking:

As mentioned earlier, member checking is an important component of making qualitative research reliable and trust worthy (Candela, 2019, p. 1). The process involves contacting interviewees again after analysis to get confirmation of "the credibility of the information" (Creswell and Miller, 2000, p.125). In the present research, the researchers contacted the interviewees after the interpretation of data to get the confirmation of the reliability of interpretation.

5. Thematic Analysis

The three interviews provided the data. They were transcribed and then analyzed using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is used to extract the information from the qualitative data such as interviews. "TA is essentially a method for identifying and analyzing patterns in qualitative data" (Clarke and Braun, 2013, What is thematic analysis? para. 1). "This critical stage in the research process involves the researcher making analytical conclusions from the data presented as codes and then themes." Here the data changes its form from "raw" to "codes" which later are transformed into "themes" which finally take the form of interpretation (Castleberry and Nelson, 2018, p. 6).

5.1. Analysis:

The data gathered via interviews of ESL tutors displays different perceptions based on their personal and contextual experiences. The iterative readings of the data and its transcription help strain the initial codes. Later these coded were compared and analyzed. These thoughts and perceptions derived from the codes shed light on the matter of teachers' autonomy and provide invaluable insight into the matter.

- I. The first theme which came to surface from data is decisions about curriculum, methodology, materials and assessment. The response from the interviewee no.1, that is, tertiary level tutor, is that decisions of pedagogical matters are delegated to administration mostly. She mentions Administration has already designed their curriculum, methodology, materials assessment everything and they have devised an outline for the faculty. While the second interviewee, instructor at college level states that these decisions are taken by higher authorities, that is, National Curriculum Council, NCC. So tutors ought to adhere to the curriculum. Teachers are not delegated power to take decisions about pedagogical matters. She informs that, National Curriculum Council, NCC designs the curriculum and syllabus. Teachers have no freedom to decide about curriculum, methodology and assessments. As far as school is concerned, secretariat makes decisions about curriculum, methodology, materials and assessment. In line with this, "organizational constraints imposed by the school and curriculum provided by state governance" (Hopmann, 2003). It is rightly said, "in reality teachers have considerable responsibility to implement decisions but little influence over the decisions" (Wermke, 2019, p. 4).
- II. The second significant theme emerged from the data is freedom to reschedule classes and to giving input in the timetable. The analysis shows that the matters about timetable and reschedule of classes vary depending on the institution. ESL practitioners in university have some freedom about time table. They are also allowed to reschedule to a limited extent. However, at college level there is no concept of taking teachers' opinion before setting timetable. It is set by some committee inside the institution. Furthermore, they cannot reschedule classes in case of emergency. Teachers are neither given freedom to reschedule their classes nor do they have choice of timings of classes. Thus, ESL teachers at school level do not have say in these matters. The Participant 3 says we don't have freedom to reschedule classes and to give our input in the timetable.
- III. The third point of concern is monitoring and surveillance of pedagogical process and uploading teaching materials on any database or LMS. The universities are well equipped in terms of technology. Therefore they have proper system of surveillance

and keeping check on pedagogical activities. The tertiary level instructor declares pedagogical material and recorded lectures are uploaded on LMS. LMS and whatsapp is under surveillance of HODs. Colleges, on the contrary, are not equipped enough to have any data base for learning management. As far as public sector schools are concerned, they were not equipped to have a system for online method of teaching before Covid-19. But as a result of Covid-19 breakout schools managed systems to resume the learning process. The school teacher informs about classes and monitoring in these words, it's monitored by observations and by matching the video tutorial we made. Actually we have not been uploading the materials on LMS before the Covid-19.

- IV. The next theme emerged out of interviewees' experiences is the impact of teachers' autonomy on the pupils' learning outcomes. All three interviewees opined that autonomous tutors take pedagogical decisions keeping in mind the learners' need and other related factors. As a result, their learners perform better. The university ESL instructor emphasized value of tutors' autonomy in these words; Teachers at school level are not delegated power to take decisions regarding their pedagogical matters. It is only the tutors at tertiary level that ESL instructor can exercise certain interventions regarding their students' better learning. Thus the findings of this aspect are in line with Wermke's ideas. He states, "Teacher autonomy depends on different contextual factors such as regimes of governance or educational traditions" (Wermke, 2019, p. 2). Similarly, "Autonomy is perceived differently in various contexts and cultures" (Paradis et al.2019, p.13).
- V. The next theme emerged from interviews' data is about the course contents. Then teachers in universities are delegated freedom to select their course contents. It is because of the fact that in the beginning of the term they are provided a course outline set by Higher Education Commission of Pakistan. The outline is general where the focus is objectives, not the pedagogical materials and books. So tutors are in a position to design their syllabus in the light of the HEC outline and students' needs. According to the interviewee, the teachers in universities can make changes in the syllabus and the course outline up to forty per cent. She states, Teacher are provided general outlines formulated by HEC and they have freedom to make changes up to 40 per cent. Whereas in the colleges, the English language course is prescribed in detail by Curriculum Course Committee. Consequently, ESL tutors are not in a position to take any decision regarding course contents.
- VI. The other theme coming under the umbrella of teacher autonomy is related to the previous discussion, that is, teachers' freedom regarding adding or reducing the course contents according to needs of students and situation. In this matter university teachers are autonomous. Keeping in view unforeseen situations they are allowed reducing course contents sometimes. Therefore the prescribed out line, they are provided are general, they can make some changes in material. They are also free to add or reduce some course contents keeping in view the learners and outer influential factors. But this is rare. In normal circumstances, we have to follow and complete the course contents. However, at primary and secondary levels teachers are not allowed to add or reduce some of the course contents. The college ESL instructor states, we, the teachers don't have the authority to add or delete anything in the prescribed course content. We have to cover the whole content during set time and we have to remain stick to the predesigned curriculum and recommended textbook. It was only allowed for the first time at college level to reduce some course contents on the account of Covid-19 and resulted online classes. It is rightly said,

Teaching profession includes the more responsibility and little power (Ingersoll, 2011, p.103).

- VII. Another significant theme emerged out of the data is the freedom of designing the activities for the classroom. At college level, very little freedom is delegated to tutors to design the activities for learners. Teachers are not autonomous in terms of designing activities for the classroom. Similarly, at school level, the matter is in the hands of administration. Some schools delegate limited freedom to teachers. However, at tertiary level, ESL tutors avail more freedom in terms of designing activities. They do design various activities to enhance learning process and to engage and motivate their learners.
- VIII. As far as teachers' opinion regarding process or the product oriented pedagogy and the emphasis of their institution is concerned, data provides different views. The university ESL practitioner believes in process oriented pedagogy and considers it during assessments as well to a limited extent though. On the contrary, the college tutor believes in product oriented pedagogy. The primary focus of instructors at secondary level is not the students' learning but their results. As far as the school level is concerned,
- IX. Another noteworthy factor regarding teachers' autonomy is selection of the assessment criteria. In universities, assessments are designed by teachers themselves but under strict instructions/ marks division by the institutions. But the exams are marked and evaluated by the instructors themselves. The case is entirely different in colleges. ESL tutors have no role in the assessment of their pupils. The exam papers are designed and evaluated by other practitioners in the field in some other region of the country. The college English language instructor declares, we have summative type of assessments at the end of the session, at the end of the whole year in colleges so assessment criteria for Federal Board we cannot choose so they have proper objective type, subjective type questions so we cannot choose assessment criteria.

Hence, the perceptions of the ESL tutors at school, college and university levels vary depending on the contextual and institutional variations.

6. Findings

The findings reveal that ESL instructors' responsibilities and domain of freedom vary according to the institution and the level. The analysis suggests that in Pakistani academic discourse community, ESL instructors at university level avail more autonomy than those working in college and school. To put it another way, the analysis reveals that teachers' duties and working boundaries vary depending on the level and institution. In the same vein, Paradis states, the concept of tutor autonomy varies depending on the context (Paradis, et al. 2019, p. 2). There are many obstacles impeding teachers' autonomy such as administrative bodies of their respective institutions and the prevalent system which supports limitations and provides very little freedom to tutors.

7. Discussion

The ESL tutors internationally have little freedom in the matters which are directly related to their job description. Teachers usually have little voice over the matter of their

own profession (Ingersoll, 2011, p. 101). Teaching profession demands multi-dimensional responsibilities. These responsibilities encompass classroom management, designing pedagogical activities, dealing with mixed ability groups of learners as well as constraints imposed by the administration (Erss, 2017, p. 2). But teachers' autonomy must be regulated to safeguard standardization of the learning across the country (Erss, 2018, p. 11).

8. Conclusion

In a nutshell, this research provides insights into the perceptions on teachers' autonomy that it underpins the processes of decision-making and control. All instructors on various levels value teachers' autonomy. However, in Pakistani context, in academia, pedagogical decisions are generally made by the administration. In addition, ESL tutors have very little freedom about the things which are directly associated to their work. At tertiary level, instructors avail some freedom but at college and school level, teachers have no contribution in decision making in terms of curriculum, methodology, materials and assessment. Teacher autonomy differs from one context to another (Paradis, et al. 2019, p. 2). It depends on institutional, cultural and historical contexts of education system in different countries (Erss, 2018, p. 16). But unguarded autonomy is not fruitful for ESL practitioners.

In a country plagued with unforeseen circumstances as strikes and political upheavals, teachers must be delegated power and autonomy to make the pedagogical process successful. The professional autonomy of tutors can be categorized as the strategies instructors have in dealing with the problems (Erss and Kalmus, 2018, p. 96). It is because teachers and students are the main bodies in the teaching learning process since teachers are in direct contact with learners so they understand their learning needs and learning ways better. Therefore, the instructors should have autonomy in terms of class execution and in policy making decisions.

9. Limitations

There are certain limitations in the research. The data were collected with a single data collection instrument, semi-structured interviews, which provides self-reported data which might be inclined to be biased (Grimm, 2010). That is, the participants might have stated their practices as better than their actual condition. Another limitation was that the study included a small number of teachers so the findings are not applicable to ESL practitioners across the country. Nevertheless, some patterns were discovered which provide pause for thought.

10. Further Research

This small scale research may inspire more comparative research in the domain of ESL practitioners in particular and in other disciplines in general on a large scale. The study may also be replicated including public as well as private sector institutions. Secondly, the study might be replicated by triangulating, adding field observation to get a more comprehensible overview of teachers' related practices.

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